

HOW LEADERSHIP STYLES AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AFFECTED EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION AT PRIVATE UNIVERSITY?

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Abstract

Leadership styles and emotional intelligence are needed in improving employee performance. Job satisfaction as a connecting variable in predictive leadership styles and emotional intelligence to employee performance. Emotional intelligence is a psychological ability that must be possessed by employees to deal with various situations. The study used the Partial Least Square (PLS) method. This method is used to analyze the implications of influences between variables of both direct and indirect effects. Relationships between variables can be analyzed in specifics and details. The results explained that emotional intelligence affects employee performance and job satisfaction. Leadership styles only affect job satisfaction. Job satisfaction affects employee performance. Emotional intelligence has the highest predictive value for employee performance. Leadership styles have no effect on employee performance. Emotional intelligence shows as a strategic ability owned by universities. The culture of religiousness that the university has synergizes positively with the emotional aspect. Job satisfaction shows emotional intelligence has positive implications for employee performance. Leadership styles have a negative effect on employee performance.

Keywords: Leadership Styles, Emotional Intelligence, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

The world of education is one of the landscape descriptions to show quality of human resources owned by a country. Quality educational organizations come from the performance of human resources. Lecturers and staff are the main actors in achieving the vision and mission of higher education institutions. The Chancellor is the highest leader of the university who must prioritize the leadership style according to the goals of the organization. The success of achieving performance cannot be separated from the leadership style. This component is needed to create a process of delegation approach and coordination to all employees. Leadership style is one aspect in the success of achieving the vision and mission of the organization. (Asmawi, 2018; Mwesigwa et al., 2020). Academic quality and excellent service are the main indicators. The performance factor of a university leader will be assisted by all his staff. The accuracy of leadership style and managerial ability is a skill that must be possessed by a leader in achieving organizational targets.

Leadership style is a pattern used by a leader in influencing the behavior of others or his troops (Akanji et al., 2020; Alshammri & Alenezi, 2021). Each leader has a different leadership style, according to the person's character and personality. That way the leadership style applied by a leader becomes one of the important factors for the success of higher education institutions. Leadership style has a positive effect on the delegation process, coordination, and communication to all employees. These three processes are crucial depending on leadership

skills. High quality performance requires a leader who understands the achievement of organizational goals. Employees urgently need a leadership style that is able to bring the right direction according to the organization's goals. Good performance will result in high competitiveness for universities. Leaders must be able to adapt to various conditions. This is influenced by a positive emotional state, a sense of pleasure from the results of the assessment of the work that has been done by employees. The satisfaction felt by employees for the work they do is not only about their attitude towards the work itself but can also include the rewards received as financial (salary) or non-financial (recognition and promotion) compensation that has been carried out professionally. This will be used as a stimulator to increase employee performance. Organizations pay attention to what employees need. Budget formulation should be directed at providing job requirements.

Performance is the final output that is measured on a quantitative and qualitative instrument of a job achievement (Baard et al., 2014; Tripathi & Agrawal, 2014). Leadership style, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction will be the driving wheel in achieving optimal performance. Staff and lecturers will work together in realizing organizational targets. Excellent service to students and international-scale publications are the highest performance achievements of a university. It is interesting that these three variables will maximize performance. This study analysed the implications of leadership style, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction on improving employee performance. The process of direct effects and indirect effects will be seen between job satisfactions as a connecting variable to employee performance. Leadership styles and emotional intelligence seek to improve the quality of performance through job satisfaction. These three research variables provide the best output as an effort to improve performance strategies. The uniqueness of this research is that it uses job satisfaction as an intervening variable on employee performance. This recommendation can be used as information material to increase the productivity of human resources at the Nahdlatul Ulama Indonesia University, Jakarta.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Leadership style is a behavior, method or pattern used by a person to influence, regulate, direct, encourage, invite and even instruct others to achieve a certain goal (Zakeer Ahmed et al., 2016). Leaders have different characteristics and tactics that vary according to their inherent personality. A person will be successful in carrying out his leadership if he applies a different leadership style in dealing with different situations (Amanchukwu et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2021). Several studies explain that leadership style has a positive effect on job satisfaction (AlonderEIne & Majauskaite, 2016; Bhatti et al., 2012; Ngabonzima et al., 2020). The relationship between these two variables is assumed that the implementation of leadership style can help the problems faced by employees. The ability to delegate work is expected to be able to place employees based on their skills and competencies. Effective communication directions are able to provide a quick understanding of the execution of work plans. Leadership style will determine the level of understanding of employees in achieving performance. Everyone has

their own leadership style in an organization. Leadership style discrepancy can have negative implications for the quality of performance. Leaders become role models and role models for employees.

The application of the leadership style must be adapted to the needs of the organization. This is also very influential in creating job satisfaction for employees or their subordinates. The leadership style focuses more on the ability to direct, coordinate, delegate, and participate in all employees in accordance with university goals. Leadership style will affect employee performance (Mamza et al., 2019; Ohemeng et al., 2018). Leaders will be able to become problem solvers for problems faced by employees. Different situations must be adapted by the leader. Every performance achievement there will be problems faced by employees. Stability of performance achievement will be easily passed by employees. The two hypotheses will be analyzed in this research model as follows:

H1: Leadership style has a positive effect on job satisfaction

H2: Leadership style has a positive effect on employee performance

Emotional Intelligence on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Emotional intelligence is an ability possessed by humans to apply knowledge and development during their lifetime (Mattingly & Kraiger, 2019). This form of intelligence is the result of training based on experience, life expression, conflict management, and problem solving that correlates with maturity of thought. Good emotional abilities will be seen in the focus of completing work. Employees who are able to control their emotions, self-situation, and separate personal problems with work professionalism are directly proportional to the quality of work results. The elements that make up emotional intelligence are the intra-personal realm, the interpersonal realm, stress control, self-adjustment, and generalization of moods (Prentice et al., 2020). This is a challenge for organizations that want emotional intelligence to be part of employee competence.

Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on job satisfaction (A. Khan et al., 2017; Suleman et al., 2020; Wen et al., 2019). Emotional intelligence is also a key component that a person must have in dealing with changing situations in the work environment. This is what causes emotional intelligence to be one of a person's abilities and skills in responding to environmental changes. This will have a positive effect on the results of strategic decisions that are able to direct employees to achieve organizational goals. It is proven from emotional intelligence in the form of self-awareness and proper emotional management can affect a person's mental condition so that it triggers job satisfaction felt by employees (Knežević et al., 2021; Tagoe & QuarshEI, 2017). This study develops emotional intelligence as measured by self-awareness, adjustment, empathy, responsibility and interpersonal relationships.

The form of emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance (Naz et al., 2019; Oyewunmi et al., 2015; Sancoko et al., 2019). Achieving performance requires a calm psychological state, focus, and passion. Optimal performance can be done with positive emotions. Employees must be formed emotional intelligence in dealing with various situations.

Stress control and optimism must exist as a form of confidence in achieving the performance set by the organization (Weiß, 2020). The ability to interact with other people is needed in working as a group. Some group assignments require cooperation, solidity, and cohesiveness among team members.

H3: Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on job satisfaction

H4: Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance.

Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

Job satisfaction as a result of employees' perceptions in carrying out work and the benefits of results on work targets (Robbins & Judge, 2018). This can be expressed as a positive or happy feeling from a job that has been done based on the results of an evaluation with certain assessment conditions or characteristics. Satisfaction felt by employees for work in the form of rewards received as financial compensation (salary) or non-financial (recognition and promotion of work that has been done well. Indicators of forming job satisfaction include job descriptions, financial compensation, benefits, non-financial compensation, support from colleagues, and support from superiors (Wagner & Hollenbeck, 2015). Several studies have shown that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance (Ekpenyoung Nkereuwem & Ekpenyoung Alfred, 2016; Razak et al., 2018; Roberts & David, 2020). Job satisfaction will have a positive effect on high quality work. Organizational expectations of performance targets can be met properly by employees. Job satisfaction can be a trigger for achieving high quality performance. The formulation of a good recognition system will create high employee loyalty to the organization. Consumer satisfaction from students and the community for the work of employees can catalyze the name of the organization both on a national and international scale.

H5: Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance.

METHOD

This research was conducted at the Indonesian Nahdlatul Ulama University, Jakarta. Sampling uses a stratified approach. This approach adopts several criteria according to the research context. The criteria for respondents are employees who work in universities and have a minimum of 2 years of tenure. The basis for taking this criterion is based on research information needs. The research data will represent the total population. Availability of data must exist for predictive interpretation of research models. Total sampling is 100 respondents from a total of 149 employees who work in universities. Respondents are employees and lecturers who work at the Nahdlatul Ulama Indonesia University, Jakarta. Leadership style is measured by indicators including decision making, providing employee motivation, communication skills, and controlling subordinates (Bashir, 2016; Sethuraman & Suresh, 2014). Indicators used to represent emotional intelligence include self-awareness, adjustment, empathy, and responsibility (Sánchez et al., 2020; Schutte & Loi, 2014). Job satisfaction is measured by indicators consisting of interpersonal relationships, employee work, job suitability, salary, and work environment (Aziri, 2011; Haider et al., 2018; Matthews et al.,

2018) . Employee performance is measured by indicators consisting of individual abilities, leadership, work teams, management systems, and workplace situations (Rohman et al., 2021; Soelistya & Gamal, 2018). The scale used is 5, namely 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (agree), and 5 (strongly agree). Below is a picture of the research model as follows:

Figure 1: Research Model

This research will use Partial Least Square (PLS) method. This method is suitable for analysing the relationship between exogenous variables (latent independent) and endogenous variables (latent dependent) (Joe F. Hair et al., 2014). The initial stage will analyze the feasibility of variable indicators with an outer loading value of more than 0.6 and a maximum of 0.7. Then, test the validity and reliability on each variable construct with Cronbach Alpha, Rho, and Composite Reliability values above 0.7 (Surucu & Maslakci, 2020). The extraction value on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is above 0.5. The next stage looks at the determination between variables with an R-Square value that is close to the absolute value (100%). It is concluded that between variables have a strong correlation to employee performance.

Hypothesis testing using T-test with p-values less than 0.5 and T-Statistics greater than T-Table (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019). Then the research hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is a positive influence between variables. Leadership styles and emotional intelligence are assumed to have an effect on employee performance through job satisfaction. This study analysed the indirect effect with the same indicators on hypothesis testing. This indirect effect analysed the influence between variables, both using a liaison through job satisfaction and directly on employee performance. The best model for improving employee performance at the university level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Partial Least Square

The next process is to analyze the data using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method. The initial stage is to analyze the feasibility of the indicator using the outer loading value that must be greater than 0.7. Below is the value of the research indicators as follows:

Table 2: Feasible Variables Indicator

Indicator	Outer Loading	Information
LS1	0.753	Feasible
LS2	0.735	Feasible
LS3	0.842	Feasible
LS4	0.802	Feasible
LS5	0.815	Feasible
LS6	0.864	Feasible
LS7	0.789	Feasible
LS8	0.773	Feasible
LS9	0.765	Feasible
LS10	0.805	Feasible
LS11	0.845	Feasible
EI1	0.768	Feasible
EI2	0.785	Feasible
EI3	0.791	Feasible
EI4	0.856	Feasible
EI5	0.836	Feasible
EI6	0.854	Feasible
EI7	0.837	Feasible
EI8	0.769	Feasible
EI9	0.846	Feasible
JS1	0.775	Feasible
JS2	0.727	Feasible
JS3	0.746	Feasible
JS4	0.776	Feasible
JS5	0.842	Feasible
JS6	0.734	Feasible
JS7	0.761	Feasible
JS8	0.844	Feasible
JS9	0.769	Feasible

EP1	0.819	Feasible
EP2	0.831	Feasible
EP3	0.903	Feasible
EP4	0.858	Feasible
EP5	0.886	Feasible
EP6	0.913	Feasible
EP7	0.830	Feasible
EP8	0.743	Feasible
EP9	0.892	Feasible
EP10	0.841	Feasible
EP11	0.790	Feasible

The results above show that all indicators of the research variables are worthy of being used as a database. The value of outer loading on all indicators is above 0.7 and is in accordance with the feasibility standards of research data (Shmueli et al., 2019). Leadership styles, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, and employee performance can be tested for hypotheses in the research model. It aims to see the predictive value that has implications for employee performance. However, in the next stage, the validity, reliability, and consistency of construct extraction will be tested on all variable indicators. Below is a table of validity, reliability, and construct values as follows:

Table 3: Validity & Reliability

Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho-A	Composite Reliability	AVE
Leadership Styles	0.943	0.944	0.951	0.635
Emotional Intelligence	0.937	0.941	0.947	0.667
Job Satisfaction	0.917	0.920	0.931	0.602
Employee Performance	0.960	0.965	0.965	0.718

The table above shows that all research data meets the aspects of validity, reliability, and consistency of indicator extraction values. Cronbach Alpha, Rho-a, and Composite Reliability values above 0.7 (Sarstedt et al., 2019). Then the consistency of indicator extraction is shown in the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value above 0.5. It can be concluded that the data can be used as a basis for research interpretation. The next stage will look at the amount of determination in leadership styles and emotional intelligence that is linked by job satisfaction to employee performance. Below is the amount of determination through the R-Square value as follows:

Table 4: R-Square

Variables	R Square
Job Satisfaction	0.482
Employee Performance	0.518

The results above explain that leadership styles and emotional intelligence simultaneously have a strong determination of job satisfaction of 48.2% and the rest is influenced by other variables outside the research model. At the same time, leadership styles and emotional intelligence which are linked through job satisfaction have a strong determination towards employee performance of 51.8%. The rest are influenced by other variables outside the context of the research model. It can be concluded that there is a strong correlation between variables on employee performance. The process of data analysis will become more specific through hypothesis testing. The process of answering the relationship between variables becomes more detailed and comprehensive. The next process is testing the hypothesis between variables partially. Below is a table of hypothesis test results as follows:

Table 5: Hypothesis Testing

Variables	Original Sample	T Statistic	P Value	Information
LS -> EP	-0.166	1.494	0.136	Rejected
LS-> JS	0.540	3.777	0.000	Accepted
EI -> EP	0.537	3.747	0.000	Accepted
EI -> JS	0.308	2.031	0.043	Accepted
JS -> EP	0.379	2.240	0.026	Accepted

The results above show that leadership styles have no effect on employee performance. The p-values are $0.136 > 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $1.494 < 1.98$ T-Table. This means that H2 is rejected and shows that leadership styles do not have any implications for employee performance. However, there are different results which show that leadership styles have a positive effect on job satisfaction. P-values $0.000 < 0.05$ and T-Statistic $3.777 > 1.98$ T-Table. This means that H1 is accepted and there are positive implications for increasing job satisfaction.

The same results were obtained between emotional intelligence and employee performance. The p-values are $0.000 < 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $3.747 > 1.98$ T-Table. This shows that H4 is accepted that emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance. Likewise, the effect of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction. The p-values are $0.043 < 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $2.031 > 1.98$ T-Table. This proves that H3 is accepted that emotional intelligence has positive implications for job satisfaction. The connecting variable of job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance. The p-values are $0.026 < 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $2.240 > 1.98$ T-Table. It can be concluded that H5 is accepted so that job satisfaction has direct implications for employee performance, especially in the university environment in achieving organizational goals.

Table 6: Indirect Effect

Variables Relationship	Original Sample	T Statistic	P Value
LS -> JS -> EP	0.205	1.870	0.062
EI -> JS -> EP	0.117	1.446	0.149

The results above indicate that there is no indirect effect in the research model. Leadership styles do not have an indirect effect on employee performance which is connected through job satisfaction. The p-values are $0.062 > 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $1.870 < 1.98$ T-Table. Emotional intelligence does not have an indirect effect on employee performance which is linked through job satisfaction. The p-values are $0.149 > 0.05$ and the T-Statistic is $1.446 < 1.98$ T-Table. Leadership styles and emotional intelligence have more direct positive implications for employee performance. This will be a separate note, especially on the job satisfaction variable as an intermediary variable that links leadership styles and emotional intelligence to improving performance. So, it can be concluded that the direct effect has more positive influence on employee performance.

DISCUSSION

This study explained that leadership styles have no effect on employee performance (Asrar-ul-Haq & Kuchinke, 2016; Makambe & Joy Motlatsi Moeng, 2020; Mawoli & Mohammed, 2013). The negative effect of leadership styles can reduce employee performance by 16.6%. However, the remaining 83.4% is still a positive indication for improvement in leadership styles in improving performance at the Nahdlatul Ulama Indonesia University, Jakarta. The results of this study should be a separate note for the problem of leadership style in the university environment. Based on appendix 2 the two lowest indicators were seen in acceptance of advice and criticism from employees (75.3%) and flexibility of freedom to employees in innovation (73.5%). These two indicators can still be improved in the process of achieving performance. These ice pros can be improved by changing the way of communication between leaders and subordinates. The effectiveness of communication can improve employees' understanding of leadership expectations. This percentage is still quite good as part of efforts to improve the performance of human resources. Lecturers and staff are catalysts for academic quality both in terms of service and the Tri Dharma of higher education (Jakubik, 2020; Kucharčíková et al., 2015). The Chancellor will be a big part in implementing the leadership style towards improving the quality of performance produced by all members of the organization.

Different results obtained on leadership style have positive implications for job satisfaction (Musinguzi et al., 2018; Rahman et al., 2018; Veerasundar & Maideen, 2019). Leadership styles are able to increase job satisfaction with a percentage of 54%. Based on appendix 2 the highest indicators are reflected in aspects of decision-making and communication skills. This indicator can be seen in the ability to create a work atmosphere (84.2%) and the rector's decisions that will be carried out by all staff (86.4%). This shows effective leadership to improve employee performance. The working atmosphere will result in high quality

productivity (Awan & Tahir, 2015; Ummatqul Qizi, 2020). Lecturers will be able to produce high-quality performance through industry-based lectures, research, and community service. The staff provides excellent service to students and lecturers. However, all that can be done through firmness in making decisions. Execution of the right decisions will result in the effectiveness of the work desired by all employees. This is what is needed in improving employee performance both from the psychological aspect of all employees.

Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance (Alferaih, 2021; Rexhepi & Berisha, 2017; Sabie et al., 2020). This variable is able to increase employee performance with a percentage of 53.7%. The results of this study are very positive towards improving the quality of performance. Based on appendix 2 indicators on the self-awareness component and four are the highest representative of the emotional intelligence variable. Empathy (85.6%) and self-awareness are willing to accept criticism from others (85.4%) are positive things in creating work conduciveness. Employees as human beings need constructive suggestions to improve the effectiveness of work processes. Humans as creatures who do not escape from mistakes cannot work individually. Building high quality work requires refinement that comes from other people's ideas. Empathy can balance work both individually and in groups (Chakrabarti & Chatterjea, 2017; Lamiani et al., 2020; Singh, 2014). Employees fill each other's gaps in competencies & skills that are not possessed by their co-workers, both in terms of work processes and performance achievement. Helping each other between employees will be the key to success in achieving high quality performance. Organizations must eliminate seniority which leads to high dependence on one person. This will be detrimental to the collective work. Building a work team requires solidity, cohesiveness, and an understanding in achieving high quality performance. This is a very good basic capital for universities in building collective work.

Emotional intelligence affects job satisfaction (Gupta et al., 2017; Lim, 2017; Ouyang et al., 2015). This variable is able to increase job satisfaction with a percentage of 30.8%. These results can be seen in the indicators of emotional control (83.7%), problem solver (84.6%), and adapting based on the situation (83.6%) (See appendix 2). Employees as humans must be able to control emotions in various situations. This means that the organization has an obligation to be able to formulate the workload in accordance with the compensation given to employees. This balance must exist to avoid too high work pressure on employees (Adeoti et al., 2020; Bartholomew et al., 2014). Emotional control is not only limited to workload, but is extended in solving work problems. Employees are given the challenge to be able to find solutions independently without the help of leaders. However, every solution found must be coordinated with the leadership so that work problems can be resolved quickly and effectively. Every problem can be resolved properly and professionally. This is a good signal to form leadership regeneration. A wealth of experience in managing organizations and contributing to work innovation. Employees can be a long-term asset to the university.

Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance (Ingsih et al., 2021; Maryati et al., 2019; Pila-Ngarm & Siengthai, 2017). This variable is able to increase employee performance with a percentage of 37.9%. This indicator can be seen from the ability of

individuals and work situations. This is explained by the achievement of good targets (89.2%), the ability to interact and cooperate among employees (90.3%), and time discipline (91.3%). A good working situation supports the achievement of optimal performance. Employees can achieve targets beyond those set by the organization. The ability to cooperate and interact is the main factor in building solid teamwork (Jones & George, 1998; Loussouarn et al., 2021). All work can be completed as a team in order to get optimal results. International publications cannot be completed individually, but form a team in the journal writing process. The same applies to academic and non-academic services to students

The results differ on the indirect effects explained by leadership styles, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction on employee performance. The research model has no indirect effect on improving employee performance. Leadership styles that are connected through job satisfaction to employee performance do not have an indirect effect. If it has an indirect effect, leadership styles are able to increase employee performance with a significant percentage of 20.5% through job satisfaction. This supports the same result where there is no direct influence between leadership styles on employee performance. Leadership styles can reduce the achievement of employee performance. Leaders at the university, faculty, and division levels must evaluate the leadership style. This will have a significant impact on employee performance. Leadership styles must be adapted to the current conditions of digitalization and rapid response to organizational changes (Hesse, 2018; S. Khan, 2016).

The same construction is formed by emotional intelligence on employee performance which is connected by job satisfaction. This variable relationship has no indirect effect. If it has an indirect effect, emotional intelligence can increase employee performance by a small percentage of 11.7% through job satisfaction. This percentage is still quite safe as an effort to achieve performance. However, the organization must think hard to provide other intelligence programs that must be owned by employees. The form of intelligence must be in line with the values of the organization. Organizational values that are built on a spiritual basis have long been embedded in all academics. Spiritual-based organizational values are very helpful in the work process (Neal & Biberman, 2004). This research model shows that emotional intelligence is the main factor in achieving high quality performance (Absah et al., 2020; Kamassi et al., 2020). Employees and lecturers are the main assets in higher education organizations. Excellent service must be carried out through a technology-based digitalization process. Research collaboration should be encouraged to increase the publicity of international research-based organizations.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that emotional intelligence is the variable with the highest implications for employee performance. Job satisfaction as a connecting variable is not able to provide an indirect effect on employee performance. The direct effect can have a significant impact through job satisfaction and emotional intelligence. Leadership styles and emotional intelligence are able to have a positive impact on job satisfaction. The application of leadership has been able to provide clarity in terms of delegation, coordination, and direction to all

employees. Emotional intelligence shows employees are able to absorb organizational values through self-control, work situations, and job responsibilities.

This research provides recommendations for increasing leadership capacity. The value of transformational leadership is very suitable for organizational change processes. Universities have to think about the development of human resources. Achievement of world-class universities can be achieved in three components, namely human resource qualifications, high quality academics, and international-based research. These three things can be done through increasing the scale of human resources. Increased competence must be based on human capital. The university has human resources with the best qualifications and specifications according to changing demands. Therefore, achieving international scale will be easier due to having highly competitive human resources.

University as an academic forum in creating superior human resources and the nation's next generation. Organizations must continue to grow and develop according to business demands. Leadership styles must be flexible and responsive to change. This component must have a strategic impact on the performance of human resources. The application of leadership with real examples will be a new stimulator for employee performance. Another approach can be taken to replace the connecting variables such as organizational commitment, employee engagement, or human capital. The connecting variables in this model can be adjusted according to the research context.

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